

Multiband Characterization of Radio Propagation Into and Inside Vehicles

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Abstract—In-vehicle subnetworks are expected to support localized and high performance connectivity within, and into, a vehicle for sixth generation (6G) communication systems. As vehicles are not specifically designed with future generation wireless systems in mind, it is crucial to investigate multi-band channel characteristics of both in-vehicle and Outdoor-to-vehicle scenarios to design 6G systems in such environments for both system optimization and interference analysis. This paper presents channel measurements in the foregoing scenarios at multiple bands including FR1, FR2, FR3 (7-24 GHz), and sub-THz. Comprehensive analysis has been conducted in terms of attenuation, fading characteristics and angular and delay dispersion based on multidimensional channel measurements on a few different real-world car models.

Index Terms—Outdoor-To-Vehicle propagation, in-vehicle propagation, multiband characterization, channel propagation, and experimental measurements.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the next ten years, 6G is expected to interconnect billions of devices, including vehicles, robots, and drones, into a highly data-intensive “network of networks” [1]. Therefore, a crucial aspect is the creation of ultra-short-range, low-power ‘in-X’ subnetworks: self-contained radio cells embedded inside robots, cars, factory modules, and other vertical market assets, which can seamlessly federate with the wider 6G fabric [2]–[6]. Modern vehicles are rapidly evolving into multi-sensor, multi-compute, networked cyber-physical systems. In this context, achieving the deterministic latency, reliability, and security required by safety-critical applications, such as automated driving, coordination in Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) and Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) networks, over-the-air updates, and immersive infotainment, critically depends on an accurate and physically grounded understanding of electromagnetic propagation. In particular, reliable system design hinges on precise modeling of how radio waves behave both when entering the cabin from the outside and when propagating within

the passenger compartment. Without dedicated in-vehicle and Outdoor-To-Vehicle (O2V) channel measurements across sub-6 GHz, millimeter-wave (mm-wave), and sub-Terahertz (sub-THz) bands, every layer of the 6G vehicular communication stack, from antenna engineering to MAC scheduling and safety certification, would be built on guesswork rather than evidence, considered that there are no standards for the design of vehicles to be compliant with 6G. Comprehensive empirical campaigns turn that uncertainty into quantifiable design margins, accelerate standardization, and unlock the weight, cost, and feature gains that next-generation connected and automated vehicles promise. Over the last two decades, a growing body of research has investigated radio propagation within vehicle interiors, particularly focusing on parked, Line-Of-Sight (LoS) or obstructed in-vehicle scenarios. Early studies concentrated on narrowband sub-6 GHz frequencies, laying the foundation for channel characterization in typical automotive environments. Zhang et al. [7] provided a modern survey in the 2.5–5 GHz range, analyzing 16 transmitter–receiver positions across the dashboard, headrests, and under-seat areas. Their results confirmed Path Loss (PL) exponents between 1.9 and 2.2 and Root-Mean Square (RMS)-Delay Spread (DS) in the 20–35 ns range. Similarly, Matolak and Chandrasekaran [8] established a 5.2 GHz baseline with 12 static links in a sedan, reporting a median RMS-DS of approximately 30 ns. Yusoff and Peng [9] extended this to Non-Line-Of-Sight (NLOS) configurations within a vehicle, including the trunk compartment, showing increased delay spreads (up to 75 ns) and reduced coherence bandwidths, highlighting challenges for robust link design in deeply obstructed paths. To explore the behavior of the wideband in-cabin channel, several studies have investigated the Ultra Wideband (UWB) range, particularly between 3 and 11 GHz. A foundational study by Schack et al. [10] provided statistically grounded measurements of key metrics such as path loss, delay spread, and small-scale fading. This dataset was later extended by Blumenstein et al. [11], who analyzed various antenna configurations and proposed statistical models for the channel transfer function. Their earlier work [12] introduced spatial stationarity, showing how small transceiver displacements can affect channel characteristics, an important consideration in dense sensor environments. Additional contributions [13], [14] examined the impact of vehicle geometry and proposed complementary shadowing models. Together, these works form the empirical basis for Saleh-Valenzuela-type intravehicle channel models. A related research direction focused on specific sub-regions, such as the engine bay, where propagation differs from the passenger cabin. Demir et al. [15],

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using UWB measurements, characterized this area, identifying notable differences in attenuation and multipath richness, and provided a full parametric model of the engine-bay channel, highlighting the importance of location-specific modeling.

Several studies have investigated mm-wave propagation inside passenger vehicles, particularly in the 55–65 GHz range. In [16], wideband measurements were conducted to extract key parameters such as PL, RMS-DS, and Multipath Component (MPC) clustering. The results indicate a reduction in RMS-DS and an increase in PL exponent compared to sub-6 GHz bands. More recently, Yamakawa et al. [17] analyzed double-directional MPCs at 61.5 GHz using horn antenna scans, showing that dominant paths cluster around the windshield LoS, while weaker components arrive via rear windows and structural elements. These findings underscore the increased sparsity, directional concentration, and blockage sensitivity of mm-wave in-vehicle channels.

The current benchmark for multiband, single-campaign in-cabin channel characterization is the comprehensive study by Li et al. [18]. Using consistent antenna placements in both a passenger car and a van, the study extracts Channel Impulse Responses (CIRs) across sub-6GHz, mm-wave, and sub-THz bands, compares RMS-DS and angular spread, and highlights increased multipath sparsity at 100 GHz. In [19], key channel parameters such as path loss and temporal dispersion are further analyzed across the same bands, with additional campaigns extending measurements beyond 100 GHz. This work specifically investigates in-vehicle links in the D-Band (110–170 GHz), a promising range for early 6G deployments. Moreover, [19] presents a preliminary assessment of penetration losses, emphasizing the severe attenuation challenges at these high frequencies.

Although the majority of studies on in-vehicle wireless propagation focus on scenarios with both transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) located inside the vehicle, a smaller body of literature has also investigated O2V links. These works primarily focus on UWB propagation at lower frequencies, particularly in the sub-6 GHz range [20]–[22], and are generally constrained to specific measurement setups and conditions, with limited frequency coverage and generalizability. To the best of our knowledge, there is a lack of experimental studies examining O2V links at higher frequencies, particularly in the FR3 band, mm-wave and in the sub-THz range.

In this paper, we address these limitations by presenting a comprehensive multiband characterization of both in-vehicle and O2V links based on an extensive measurement campaign. Building on previous works [18], [19], we contribute new data focused on realistic vehicular scenarios and cover a wide frequency range. Our study provides new insights into high-frequency vehicular channels by analyzing key propagation characteristics, such as link attenuation, fading statistics, angular dispersion, and multipath characteristics, which remain largely unexplored in these bands. The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- Characterization of link attenuation in realistic in-vehicle and O2V scenarios across multiple Frequency Ranges (FRs), with emphasis on identifying critical frequency-dependent propagation losses.

- Analysis of the Rician K-factor for in-vehicle links, highlighting the impact of frequency and antenna configuration on fading behavior and LoS dominance.
- Evaluation of delay and angular dispersion parameters, including RMS-DS and angular spread, and investigation of spatial multipath propagation through directional and temporal profiling of MPCs, supported by comparisons with realistic environmental geometries.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the measurement equipment, the considered scenarios, and outlines the procedure used to derive the propagation parameters. Section III presents the main results in terms of attenuation from different car components in several frequency bands. In Section IV, the multipath propagation characteristics are analyzed in detail by extracting fading statistics, and angular and delay dispersion characteristics. Finally, Section V provides the conclusions.

II. MEASUREMENT EQUIPMENT AND SCENARIOS

In this section, we provide a detailed description of the measurement setups employed for the different scenarios, including in-vehicle and O2V links. Measurements were conducted at both the University of Bologna (Cesena campus) and Aalborg University. We have performed measurements on three different vehicle models and across different frequency ranges to achieve a complete characterization of the propagation parameters. The considered vehicle models are: Mercedes-Benz 200D, Tesla Model Y, and SEAT Leon. The FRs investigated are FR1 (sub-6GHz), FR2 (above 24.25 GHz), FR3 (7.125 – 24.25 GHz), W-Band (75–110 GHz) and D-Band (110–170 GHz). In particular, Obstructed-Line-Of-Sight (OLOs) measurements were performed to investigate the impact of signal attenuation by internal and external car components. For in-vehicle OLoS and O2V-OLoS scenarios, we used directional antennas as Tx and Rx and we analyzed two frequency ranges: 8 – 12 GHz and 110 – 170 GHz. Furthermore, a measurement campaign was conducted in an in-vehicle LoS environment to characterize propagation for in-cabin wireless links, using omnidirectional antennas over three frequency ranges: 4 – 6.5 GHz, 25 – 27.5 GHz and 99 – 101.5 GHz. All measurements were performed with a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) setup, and details of the measurement equipment and frequency bands are shown in Table I.

A. In-Vehicle Measurement Scenarios

We set up two different deployments, shown in Fig. 1 and 2: in-vehicle LoS measurements (Scenario 1), to characterize short-range propagation links in the car cabin, and in-vehicle OLoS (Scenario 2), to evaluate the signal attenuation from internal car's components.

For in-vehicle LoS measurements, omni-directional antenna were used at both link ends, and Tx was positioned on the vehicle dashboard, while Rx was placed at three different locations illustrated in Fig. 1: close to the front-right side window (Scenario 1.A), next to the backrest of the front seat (Scenario 1.B), and on the backrest of the rear center

TABLE I: Measurements equipment and key specifications.

Equipment setup	Model	Key specifications
<i>Measurement equipment at FR1 (4-6.5 GHz) frequencies</i>		
VNA	Keysight PNA-X N5242B	Frequency: 10MHz - 26.5GHz
Transmitter	Planar monopole (omni)	Gain: 2 dBi, Pol.: V
Receiver	Planar monopole (omni)	Gain: 0 dBi, Pol.: V
<i>Measurement equipment at FR3 (8-12 GHz) frequencies</i>		
VNA	Keysight PNA-X N5242B	Frequency: 10MHz - 26.5GHz
Transmitter	Horn ARRA x820	Gain: 16-18 dBi, Polarization: V
Receiver	Horn ARRA x820	Gain: 16-18 dBi, Polarization: V
<i>Measurement equipment at mm-wave (25-27.5 GHz) frequencies</i>		
VNA	VNA (R&S ZNA 43)	Frequency: 10MHz - 43.5GHz
Transmitter	Biconical (omni-directional) [23]	Gain: 4 dBi, Pol.: V
Receiver	Biconical (omni-directional) [23]	Gain: 4 dBi, Pol.: V
Rotating Receiver	Standard gain horn (Flann 21240) [24]	Gain: 20 dBi, Pol.: V
<i>Measurement equipment at W-Band (99-101.5 GHz) frequencies</i>		
VNA	VNA (R&S ZNA 43)	Frequency: 10MHz - 43.5GHz
VNA Extender modules	VDI WR10-VNAX [25]	Frequency: 75-110 GHz
Transmitter	Biconical (omni-directional) [26]	Gain: 2 dBi, Pol.: V
Receiver	Biconical (omni-directional) [26]	Gain: 2 dBi, Pol.: V
Rotating Receiver	Standard gain horn (Flann 27240) [24]	Gain: 20 dBi, Pol.: V
<i>Measurement equipment at D-Band (110-170 GHz) frequencies</i>		
VNA	Keysight PNA-X N5242B	Frequency: 10MHz - 26.5GHz
VNA Extender modules	VDI WR6.5-VNAX [27]	Frequency: 110-170 GHz
Transmitter	VDI Conical horn WR 6.5 [28]	Gain: 20-22 dBi, Pol.: V
Receiver	VDI Conical horn WR 6.5 [28]	Gain: 20-22 dBi, Pol.: V

seat (Scenario 1.C). For in-vehicle OLoS measurements (see Fig. 2), directional horn antennas are used at both link ends, Tx and Rx are positioned facing each other, with the Tx placed on the driver’s side and the Rx located behind the driver’s seat. In particular, two different situations are analyzed, both representative of typical OLoS condition: in Scenario 2.A, the antennas are on the seats, and the seat backrest acts as an obstruction; in Scenario 2.B, Tx and Rx are placed on the floor, with the signal path obstructed by under-seat structures. The latter case is representative of a typical situation where wireless nodes are deployed at floor level, and a wireless link must be established between Electronic Control Units (ECUs) located in different zones of the car cabin, e.g. rear and front [29].

A further setup exploiting the widely used Directional Scan Sounding (DSS) scheme [30], [31] is also employed to perform channel spatial analysis. This approach typically employs a directional antenna and captures signals from various angles using a mechanical rotator. In our measurements, a horn antenna is used at Rx side, which rotates 360 degrees in azimuth with a step of 10 degrees, compliant with Rx antenna half power beam width. For the DSS measurements (Scenario 3.A), the Tx omni antenna and the rotating Rx horn antenna were both located on the rear seats of the vehicle at a distance of 0.9 m, as shown in Fig. 3.

B. Outdoor-To-Vehicle Measurement Scenarios

In order to estimate the link attenuation caused by the vehicle’s external structure, we conducted measurements in four specific configurations. In all cases, the Tx was aligned with the Rx both horizontally and vertically. The Rx was placed in the following positions: i) on the driver’s seat, facing the window (simulating transmission through the side window); ii) on the driver’s seat, facing the door (through the vehicle body); iii) inside the hood, facing its door; iv) inside the trunk, facing the trunk door.

For the FR3 band, we also performed measurements to investigate spatial propagation in two O2V-OLoS scenarios

using the DSS scheme described in Section II.A, with the horn Rx antenna mounted on a mechanical rotator inside the car trunk, as shown in Fig. 4. In the first scenario, denoted as Scenario 4.A and shown in Fig. 4 (a), the Tx was placed outside the vehicle with its antenna aperture directed towards the trunk. In the second scenario, defined as 4.B and shown in Fig. 4 (b), Tx was positioned outside the vehicle at the rear side, with its antenna aperture horizontally and vertically aligned towards the rear door of the car.

C. Derivation of Propagation Parameters

The derivation of propagation parameters is based on the Power-Delay Profiles (PDPs) obtained from the measurements. The VNA records the Channel Frequency Response (CFR) $H(f)$. By applying the inverse Fourier transform to $H(f)$, with an appropriate Hamming window $W(f)$, the CIR $h(\tau)$ is obtained as follows [32]:

$$h(\tau) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}[W(f) \cdot H(f)]. \quad (1)$$

From $h(\tau)$, the normalized PDP is computed as [32]:

$$p(\tau) = |h(\tau)|^2. \quad (2)$$

When the VNA’s measurement is characterized by a large bandwidth, we subdivided the entire $H(f)$ into sub-bands since material parameters can significantly change over the considered bandwidth.

In the following 2 sections, we report the measurement results of key propagation parameters extracted from the PDPs for in-vehicle and O2V links. In Section III the signal attenuation is analyzed LoS and OLoS scenarios. In Section IV, a more detailed characterization of multipath propagation is carried out through analysis of the Rician K-Factor, and of angular and temporal dispersion characteristics.

III. ATTENUATION ANALYSIS

As mentioned in the previous section, one of the purposes of this work is to analyse link losses for in-vehicle and O2V scenarios. Since measurement of OLoS links was performed with very directive antennas to counter the relatively poor power-budget, almost only the radial path was present in those cases, where transmission or reflection loss of vehicle components was derived, as explained in sections III.B - III.D. Therefore, path loss was only analyzed in LoS cases with omni antennas in order to highlight the impact of multipath reverberation within the car with respect to free space propagation.

Preliminarily, the Isotropic Path Loss value (PL_{meas}), expressed in dB, is extracted from the PDP of LoS measurements as follows:

$$PL_{\text{meas}}[\text{dB}] = -10 \log_{10} \left(\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{p_n}{G_{\text{Tx}} \cdot G_{\text{Rx}}} \right), \quad (3)$$

where G_{Tx} and G_{Rx} denote the Tx and Rx omnidirectional antenna gains and $p_n = p(\tau_n)$ represents the normalized power of the n -th MPC, which is obtained by performing a local maxima search on the PDP values exceeding a specific noise threshold, determined on the base of measurement conditions.

Fig. 1: In-vehicle LoS measurement scenarios: (a) Scenario 1.A with a link distance of 0.91 m. (b) Scenario 1.B: with a link distance of 0.88 m. (c) Scenario 1.C: with a link distance of 1.62 m. Omnidirectional antennas were used in all three setups.

Fig. 2: Illustration of in-vehicle OLoS measurement scenarios performed at 110 – 170 GHz (Tx-Rx distance 0.5 m) and 8 – 12 GHz (Tx-Rx distance 1.3 m). Directive antennas were used in all setups, with Tx and Rx placed at 25 cm above seat level in 2.A, and 10 cm above the car floor level in 2.B.

Scenario 3.A

(a) Scenario 4.A

Fig. 3: Setup for channel spatial analysis under in-vehicle LoS conditions, using a mechanical rotator at the Rx. Tx and Rx placed 35 cm above the seat level.

In substance, in (3) the incoherent sum of the most significant MPCs powers is performed to compute the local average of measured path loss in realistic conditions. Note also that the gains of the Tx and Rx antennas are de-embedded from the isotropic path loss computation.

PL_{meas} is then compared with the reference isotropic free-space path loss, given by [33]:

$$L_{\text{FS}}[\text{dB}] = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{4\pi d f_c}{c} \right), \quad (4)$$

where c is the speed of light, f_c is the center frequency of the sub-band of interest, and d is link distance.

The second part of the analysis is focused on attenuation by internal components (i.e., seat backrest and the under-seat structure) and vehicle body structures, including doors, trunk,

(b) Scenario 4.B

Fig. 4: Illustration of different O2V-OLoS measurement scenarios where spatial analysis is performed by rotating the Rx, mounted on a mechanical rotator. The Tx and Rx antennas are directional and positioned at 1 m above the ground.

hood, and window, as shown in sections III.B - III.D. As a figure of merit for OLoS propagation we consider the *penetration loss* value L_P , expressed in dB, which quantifies the excess loss (or insertion loss) along the radial path with respect to free-space condition, caused by obstructing structures. L_P is obtained by performing OLoS measurements with directive antennas in presence of the obstacle and by isolating the MPC corresponding to the radial path in the PDP through a time gating procedure. Then, the received power obtained from a calibration measurement without the obstructing object and in the same configuration (link distance, orientation of the antennas, etc.) is subtracted to the measured power to estimate insertion loss L_P . However, in many practical situations the measured penetration loss value may be influenced by additional multipath components that are very close to the radial path, for instance diffractions from the edges, or multiple internal reflections, which can generate a frequency-selective behaviour. In order to quantify the impact of such effect on the measured insertion loss as a function of the frequency, two further parameters are introduced: the mean penetration loss ($\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$) and its standard deviation ($\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$), computed directly in the frequency domain and with no time-gating, for the k -th sub-band (Δf_k). Subsequently, the link attenuation results are reported for the following scenarios: in-vehicle LoS, OLoS within the vehicle, and O2V-OLoS.

A. Link Attenuation for in-vehicle LoS scenarios

The results of PL_{meas} in comparison with L_{FS} across three frequency bands for in-vehicle LoS scenarios with omni antennas are summarized in Tab. II. Both measured and theoretical path losses increase with frequency, as they should, with Scenario 1.B consistently exhibiting the lowest loss across all bands due to the shortest link distance. In the 4 – 6.5 GHz and 25 – 27.5 GHz bands, the differences between PL_{meas} and L_{FS} are more pronounced than those at sub-THz frequencies, suggesting a stronger gain due to reverberation effect at lower frequencies. At 99 – 101.5 GHz, the differences between PL_{meas} and L_{FS} values for scenarios 1.A, 1.B, and 1.C are only of 1.64 dB, 2.23 dB, and 0.62 dB, respectively. This is attributed to the increasing dominance of the LoS path and reduced influence of secondary reflections and scattering in these scenarios at sub-THz bands.

B. Attenuation by Internal Vehicle Components

The in-vehicle OLoS measurements in the FR3 frequency band (8 – 12 GHz) highlighted that at these frequencies, the signal attenuation due to the seat backrest and under-seat obstruction is almost negligible. In particular, the values of L_P and $\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ obtained from the measurements, vary in the range from 1 to 2 dB, and remain approximately constant across the entire bandwidth.

At 110 – 170 GHz, instead, the penetration losses are more significant, as shown in Fig. 6. As expected, the penetration losses increase with frequency, and there are no significant differences between L_P and $\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$. Furthermore, it can be concluded that, in this frequency range, for some car models (i.e. Tesla Model Y) even the clutter under the seat, if

Fig. 5: Measurement setup used to analyze signal reflections from the car ceiling. The setup includes two directive antennas located 35 cm above the seat level.

present, can lead to significant signal attenuation (4 – 6 dB). More relevant are the penetration losses induced by the seat’s backrest, which vary with the vehicle’s model, materials, and thickness. For seat backrests with smaller thickness (SEAT Leon), the penetration loss values range from 8 to 10 dB, while for seat backrests with greater thickness, the attenuation can reach 15 dB. These results show that the signal transmission between Tx and Rx, positioned respectively in front of and behind the vehicle seat and horizontally aligned, can be subject to significant attenuation, especially at high frequencies.

C. Propagation through reflection on the ceiling

In this section, we present an analysis of a possible solution to ensure reliable in-vehicle connectivity in OLoS scenarios where direct paths are significantly attenuated, as shown in the previous section, or when the signal is further attenuated by passengers, making direct in-cabin radio links unfeasible. In these cases, it can be advantageous to leverage reflection from car ceiling to guarantee connectivity. Therefore, we have conducted measurements to evaluate whether it is possible to exploit this alternative propagation path. The measurement setup is shown in Fig. 5. The deployment features two directive antennas, both illuminating the same spot on the car ceiling. The antennas are positioned such that the angles between their pointing directions and the roof normal are approximately equal, in order to exploit specular reflection. The analysis is conducted on conventional steel vehicle roofs within the FR3 and FR2 frequency bands, with measured results indicating average reflection excess attenuation values of approximately 5 dB in FR3 and 8 dB in FR2. The relatively high reflection loss can be explained by observing that the car ceiling has usually additional layers of insulating materials in addition to the metal roof, that increase reflection loss. A typical ceiling structure is for instance the three-layer composite structure: knitted fabric + sponge + non-woven fabric.

In addition, measurements are performed also on the Tesla Model Y which has a laminated glass roof, with no additional layers: in such a case, an increase of about 3 dB to 5 dB in the average reflection loss is observed with respect to metal roofs, probably due to the lower reflectivity of glass with respect to metal.

TABLE II: PL_{meas} and L_{FS} values for different in-vehicle LoS scenarios (shown in Fig. 1).

Scenario	4–6.5 GHz		25–27.5 GHz		99–101.5 GHz	
	PL_{meas} (dB)	L_{FS} (dB)	PL_{meas} (dB)	L_{FS} (dB)	PL_{meas} (dB)	L_{FS} (dB)
2.A	42.52	46.03	55.76	60.01	70.00	71.64
2.B	40.51	45.73	55.02	59.71	69.12	71.35
2.C	43.66	51.04	61.31	65.01	76.03	76.65

Reflected path losses are significantly higher than the penetration losses experienced by the radial path at below-6GHz and FR3 frequencies, and of the same order of magnitude of the penetration losses at mm-wave and sub-THz, according to the results shown in Fig. 6. However, in several practical situations there are people present on the seats, introducing an additional human blockage attenuation. According to recent studies, such attenuation is in the range 20 – 50 dB at mm-wave frequencies, depending on whether the signal is partially obstructed (e.g. by arms), or fully obstructed by the human torso [34]. Further studies also showed that human body attenuation can reach values up to 70 – 80 dB in the sub-THz bands, making the wireless connection impractical [35].

Based on the foregoing results, it can be concluded that using ceiling reflection represents a possible solution with all types of roofs whenever direct connectivity is not possible at high frequencies due to human blockage.

D. Attenuation by Car Body Parts

Attenuation values are reported in Tab. III and Tab. IV. $\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ values generally follow the trend of direct path attenuation L_P , although they also reflect additional fading effects due to multipath propagation. As expected, attenuation increases with frequency; however, some deviations are observed, possibly due to frequency-selective fading or internal resonances. Although a vehicle window introduces negligible attenuation in the 8 – 12 GHz band, penetration loss can become critical in the 110 – 170 GHz range. O2V communication links, where the line-of-sight is obstructed by a car door or trunk lid, are relevant in both the 8 – 12 GHz and, more notably, at 110 – 170 GHz. High attenuation levels are observed across all door types and the highest attenuation is observed for the trunk door, with relatively similar values despite materials variations in different car models. In addition, the results suggest that the material composition may have a greater impact on attenuation than thickness, for example the presence of multiple layers in addition to metal, and the presence of cabling, mainly inside the trunk door.

At FR3 frequencies, the side door of the Tesla Model Y exhibits significantly lower attenuation, despite this car features a thicker door than the SEAT Leon. However, the explanation for this is in the different geometry of the car body and in particular the position of the window: in fact, as explained in detail in the next section, in this particular case the penetration actually occurs through signal spillover onto the edge adjacent to the window, rather than through the metal part of the door.

In the case of Tesla Model Y, the penetration loss from the car hood was also measured, since this compartment does not contain the engine, unlike in internal combustion vehicles, and thus it was possible to deploy a directional antenna inside of it. Surprisingly, a relatively low penetration loss has been observed, of the order of 10 dB at FR3 frequencies, and in the range 15 – 20 dB at sub-THz frequencies (D-band). Therefore, O2V communication with wireless nodes in the hood or engine bay appears to be possible in all frequency bands, ranging from low-frequencies to sub-THz. The explanation for this may be that the front of the car is typically made of plastic rather than metal parts, mainly the bumper, which cause relatively low signal attenuation.

Fig. 6: L_P , $\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ and $\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$ values at 110 – 170 GHz in in-vehicle OLoS scenarios, considering different vehicle's internal components and 6 GHz-wide sub-bands.

E. Detailed Analysis of Door Penetration Losses

In the following, we provide a more detailed analysis of propagation between Tx and Rx in an O2V-OLoS scenario, where the obstructing object is the vehicle's door. In fact, in several practical cases, the actual penetration of the radio signal beyond the illuminated object is caused by propagation around the object through diffractions on its edges and corners, rather than on the radial path, especially when the antennas are not very directive and the material has high losses: this is the typical case of car doors, which are composed of a sandwich with a metal layer. Since antenna directivity at FR3 is lower than at mm-wave and sub-THz frequencies, this results in a wider footprint at the same distance on the obstacle: the main

TABLE III: L_P , $\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ and $\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$ over the range from 8 to 12 GHz for each central frequency of each sub-band of 1.3 GHz, considering as obstructing structures: window, hood, door and trunk.

f_c	Tesla Model Y: Window			SEAT Leon: Window		
	8.66 GHz	10 GHz	11.33 GHz	8.66 GHz	10 GHz	11.33 GHz
L_P (dB)	0.83	0.46	1.81	2.95	2.62	1.88
$\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	0.83	0.45	1.87	2.93	2.62	1.87
$\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	0.50	0.28	0.53	0.31	0.31	0.33
f_c	8.66 GHz	Hood 10 GHz	11.33 GHz	8.66 GHz	10 GHz	11.33 GHz
L_P (dB)	9.67	8.58	7.95	–	–	–
$\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	9.68	8.85	8.15	–	–	–
$\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	1.80	1.97	1.92	–	–	–
f_c	8.66 GHz	Door 10 GHz	11.33 GHz	8.66 GHz	Door 10 GHz	11.33 GHz
L_P (dB)	14.15	15.57	17.45	21.20	23.22	24.61
$\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	14.10	15.60	17.55	21.25	23.24	24.66
$\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	1.13	1.10	1.33	1.27	1.53	1.58
f_c	8.66 GHz	Trunk 10 GHz	11.33 GHz	8.66 GHz	Trunk 10 GHz	11.33 GHz
L_P (dB)	32.96	35.39	36.93	24.43	27.84	27.83
$\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	30.83	31.26	31.72	24.44	26.16	27.62
$\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	5.91	5.77	5.07	4.43	3.94	5.04

TABLE IV: L_P , $\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ and $\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$ over the range from 110 – 170 GHz for each central frequency of each sub-band of 6 GHz, considering as obstructing structures: window, hood, door and trunk.

	f_c	113 GHz	119 GHz	125 GHz	131 GHz	137 GHz	143 GHz	149 GHz	155 GHz	161 GHz	167 GHz
Tesla Model Y Window	L_P (dB)	6.46	8.54	6.97	7.25	7.73	8.09	8.49	8.58	8.79	9.59
	$\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	7.85	7.92	7.94	7.95	8.02	8.10	8.10	8.17	8.23	8.30
	$\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	1.08	1.08	1.16	1.18	1.20	1.23	1.21	1.22	1.20	1.18
SEAT Leon Window	L_P (dB)	5.75	5.31	5.26	6.19	5.44	6.31	6.43	6.34	7.23	6.79
	$\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	5.27	5.34	5.34	5.34	5.40	5.42	5.42	5.53	5.58	5.68
	$\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	0.82	0.85	0.89	0.96	1.02	1.01	1.03	0.99	0.93	0.92
Tesla Model Y Hood	L_P (dB)	15.53	15.94	14.40	15.13	21.97	17.20	20.44	21.56	19.37	21.90
	$\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	18.85	19.60	17.65	16.93	17.71	18.51	18.75	18.21	17.90	18.77
	$\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	3.81	5.09	4.26	4.33	5.23	4.46	5.45	3.73	3.27	2.91
Tesla Model Y Door	L_P (dB)	42.12	44.45	44.86	42.06	47.19	46.30	43.60	45.14	45.44	45.82
	$\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	42.49	44.90	46.91	46.75	45.04	44.07	46.24	45.49	44.92	41.70
	$\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	5.79	5.27	5.73	5.14	5.37	5.96	6.14	4.76	6.29	4.84
SEAT Leon Door	L_P (dB)	43.27	47.96	43.89	52.61	49.80	47.13	44.61	54.43	47.88	50.74
	$\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	43.05	45.26	45.75	45.26	48.94	45.65	45.62	47.95	48.18	48.09
	$\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	4.38	4.17	5.19	6.29	4.56	5.74	4.23	6.09	4.37	5.26
Tesla Model Y Trunk	L_P (dB)	57.44	53.30	63.22	60.79	61.76	58.21	63.67	59.50	62.71	59.27
	$\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	52.75	50.92	53.82	54.76	53.80	51.88	50.56	51.46	52.50	49.84
	$\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	5.72	6.27	6.02	5.97	6.38	5.91	6.13	5.55	5.24	4.84
SEAT Leon Trunk	L_P (dB)	48.47	53.32	51.67	46.46	51.18	51.53	51.95	53.38	50.22	52.66
	$\bar{L}_{P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	50.96	48.88	52.10	52.86	51.75	50.13	49.00	49.59	50.56	47.99
	$\sigma_{L_P,\Delta f_k}$ (dB)	5.70	6.29	6.02	5.93	6.39	5.87	6.09	5.55	5.25	4.84

radiation lobe of the Tx antenna then partially illuminates the car window, causing a “spillover” that allows to reach the Rx inside the car through diffraction on the horizontal door edge adjacent to the window. In order to highlight this phenomenon, we conducted two measurements in the FR3 band (8 – 12 GHz) with the Tx outside and the Rx inside the vehicle, with the antennas placed at the same height and oriented toward the center of the door. In the first measurement, the car door is open; in the second, the door is closed, and the footprint of the antenna main radiation lobe extends partially onto the window (as shown in Fig. 7). From the comparison of the power distance profiles of these two measurements, illustrated

in Fig. 8, we can observe a shift of the main peak in the OLoS case of roughly 5 cm: this corresponds to the additional length of the edge-diffracted path compared to the radial path, thus demonstrating that the actual penetration of the signal into the car is obtained by leveraging the spillover effect. It is important to note that, given a 4 GHz bandwidth, the spatial resolution of the measurements is approximately 7.5 cm. This implies that two different paths separated by less than 7.5 cm cannot be distinguished in the power distance profile. As a result, in the OLoS case the main path between Tx and Rx will represent the combination of the direct path (shown in red in the Fig. 7) and the diffracted path on the edge of the window (shown

in green in the Fig. 7). In order to overcome this problem, an appropriate zero-padding technique is exploited during the post-processing to improve the localization of the main peak, that allows to obtain the results shown in Fig. 8.

Looking at the peak value of the PDP, it is observed a decrease of about 15 dB when the door is closed, which is compatible with a diffraction quite close to the Incidence Shadow Boundary (ISB).

This experimental result allows us to conclude that, if the Tx is not sufficiently close to the obstructing structure or when antennas with low directivity are used, O2V propagation mainly takes place because of window penetration, and this can be leveraged to provide O2V coverage, especially at lower frequencies. On the other hand, in order to optimize the performance of in-vehicle subnetworks, the use of properly oriented highly directive antennas can be exploited to achieve a good isolation and protection against signal interferences: this is the typical case of mm-wave and sub-THz frequencies.

Fig. 7: Geometric configuration of the OLoS measurements on the car door to analyze the spillover effect. Radial path length: $(2 + 0.63)$ m = 2.63 m; Diffracted Path length: $(2.01 + 0.67)$ m = 2.68 m. Tx and Rx placed at 1 m above ground.

IV. ANALYSIS OF MULTIPATH PROPAGATION

In the present section, a characterization of multipath propagation is presented. Small-scale fading characteristics are studied through analysis of the Rician K-Factor. Moreover, angular and temporal characteristics are investigated by means of Power-Angle-Delay Profiles (PADPs), RMS Angular Spread and RMS Delay Spread.

A. Rician K-factor Evaluation

This subsection reports the results related to Rician K-Factor values for the in-vehicle LoS links shown in Fig. 1. In order to estimate the Rician K-Factor values, we used the method of moments in the frequency domain, considering sub-bands of approximately 400 MHz as [36], assuming that the channel satisfies the conditions of Wide-Sense Stationary Uncorrelated Scattering. The Rician K-factor values are averaged across the sub-bands, yielding the mean value \bar{K} , expressed in dB. Tab. V reports the \bar{K} values for each frequency range. Interpreting

Fig. 8: Power distance profiles corresponding to the configuration in Fig. 7. Red curve: door open (LoS condition); Green curve: door closed (OLOs condition).

the Rician K-factor as the power ratio between the dominant signal path and the scattered multipath components, we can draw some observations from the results.

Considering the LoS scenarios reported in Tab. V and comparing the results related to scenarios 1.B and 1.C, it can be observed that, by placing the Rx on the side of the seat in the center of the vehicle at different antenna distances (0.88 m and 1.62 m), the Rician K-factor decreases as the antennas distance increases. This behaviour could be caused by the fact that the antenna footprint includes a wider area of the environment at greater distances, introducing more MPCs. Compared to Scenario 1.C, Scenarios 1.A and 1.B show more similar K-factor values. In addition, mm-wave and sub-THz scenario 1.B have an higher Rician K-factor value than Scenario 1.A. This indicates that when the Rx is placed on the inner edge of the vehicle door, the link is characterized by a stronger presence of scattered signal components. Furthermore, it is observed that as the frequency increases, the K-factor values are mostly increasing. This is probably because, at higher frequencies, multipath components experience greater attenuation than the unobstructed direct path.

TABLE V: \bar{K} values for different in-vehicle LoS scenarios with omnidirectional antennas.

K-Factor In-vehicle LoS scenarios (Fig. 1)			
Scenario	4–6.5 GHz	25–27.5 GHz	99–101.5 GHz
1.A	5.70	3.56	11.37
1.B	3.19	5.58	13.30
1.C	1.98	3.50	5.36

B. Dispersion Parameter Definitions

In the following, we will focus on the analysis of the temporal and spatial distribution of MPCs.

As a measure of the channel temporal dispersion we consider the RMS delay spread (τ_{RMS}), computed across a range of frequency bands as follows:

$$\tau_{\text{RMS}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{n=1}^N p_n (\tau_n - \bar{\tau})^2}{\sum_{n=1}^N p_n}}, \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{\tau}$ is the mean excess delay, calculated as:

$$\bar{\tau} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N p_n \tau_n}{\sum_{n=1}^N p_n}, \quad (6)$$

where τ_n and p_n are the delay and power of the n -th MPC, respectively.

The temporal dispersion is analyzed in the following in all the measurement scenarios, including in-vehicle LoS and OLoS measurements with static Tx and Rx locations.

In order to analyze in detail also the angular channel characteristics, we rely on the DSS scheme described in Section II, and we extract PADPs for the in-vehicle LoS link shown in Fig. 3 at 25 – 27 GHz and 99 – 101.5 GHz.

In addition, we have derived and examined PADPs in two different O2V-OLoS scenarios (see Fig. 4) in the 8-12 GHz band.

The overall angular dispersion is also evaluated by extracting Angle Of Arrivals (AOAs) from the PADPs and using the RMS angular spread (σ_{AS}), computed according to the following formula [37], [38]:

$$\sigma_{AS} = \min_{\Delta} \sqrt{\overline{\theta(\Delta)^2} - \bar{\theta}(\Delta)^2} \quad (7)$$

where $\bar{\theta}(\Delta)$ is the averaged angle weighted by power and is given by:

$$\bar{\theta}(\Delta) = \frac{\sum_i [P_i(\theta_i) \cdot ((\theta_i + \Delta) \bmod 2\pi)]}{\sum_i P_i(\theta_i)}, \quad (8)$$

and $\overline{\theta(\Delta)^2}$ is:

$$\overline{\theta(\Delta)^2} = \frac{\sum_i [P_i(\theta_i) \cdot ((\theta_i + \Delta) \bmod 2\pi)^2]}{\sum_i P_i(\theta_i)}, \quad (9)$$

where θ_i is the i -th AOA, and $P_i(\theta_i) = \sum_{n=1}^N p_{in}(\theta_i)$ is the total received power at θ_i , obtained through integration of the PDP. Eq. (7) ensures an unambiguous evaluation of the angular spread by accounting for the periodicity of angles modulo 2π .

In order to compute RMS delay and angular spread values, an appropriate threshold is applied to select only the paths whose power exceeds 0.1% of the main path power. This percentage is chosen to ensure that weak paths are also considered, particularly relevant in indoor environments and at relatively high frequencies.

C. Channel Dispersion Results

1) In-Vehicle Measurements with fixed antennas

LoS omni scenarios (1.A-B-C): Table VI reports RMS delay spread for scenarios 1.A–C under in-vehicle LoS conditions with omni antennas. A consistent reduction in delay spread with increasing frequency is observed, particularly in the sub-THz range, due to reduced diffraction and weaker MPCs. In Scenario 1.A, the delay spread decreases from 2.4 ns at 4 – 6.5 GHz to 0.85 ns at 99–101.5 GHz, suggesting a low-multipath environment likely influenced by favorable antenna positioning. Scenario 1.C presents the highest delay spread across all bands, indicating a more complex multipath environment with more scatterers. Even here, at 99–101.5 GHz, the delay spread reduces to 1.4 ns due to weaker scattering.

OLoS scenarios with Directive Antennas (2.A-B): For both the 8–12 GHz and 110–170 GHz frequency bands, scenarios 2.A and 2.B show consistently low τ_{RMS} with minimal variation across sub-bands. Scenario 2.A exhibits the lowest temporal dispersion, with average τ_{RMS} of 0.4 ns at 8–12 GHz and 0.09 ns at 110–170 GHz. Scenario 2.B shows slightly higher values, 0.65 ns and 0.13 ns at the same frequency bands, reflecting increased dispersion due to a more reflective environment.

TABLE VI: RMS Delay Spread values for Different in-vehicle LoS scenarios, across Various Frequency Ranges.

In-vehicle LoS scenarios			
Scenario	4 - 6.5 GHz	25 - 27.5 GHz	99 - 101.5 GHz
	τ_{RMS} (ns)	τ_{RMS} (ns)	τ_{RMS} (ns)
1.A	2.4	2.1	0.85
1.B	6.3	3.4	1
1.C	10	3.2	1.4

2) In-vehicle and O2V measurements with DSS

In-vehicle LoS link (Scenario 3.A): Fig. 9 shows the PADPs measured in Scenario 3.A for both mm-wave and sub-THz bands. In both cases, the main MPCs are confined within 15 ns, and their spatial distribution is well aligned across the bands. Minor differences in delay and AOA arise due to manual positioning inaccuracies. Four dominant MPCs, common to both the mm-wave and sub-THz bands, are marked in Fig. 9, with their corresponding trajectory shown in Fig. 10. The LoS path has an AOA of approximately 0° due to face-to-face antenna placement. Path 2, a reflection from the seat backrest, appears stronger at sub-THz frequencies, likely due to the different electromagnetic properties of the materials involved. Path 3 is a strong reflection from the side door behind the Tx antenna, while Path 4 is a double-bounce reflection that interacts with the seat back and the side door within the passenger cabin. The RMS angular spread is 30° at 25 – 27.5 GHz, and 33° at 99 – 101.5 GHz. The MPC distribution in this in-vehicle LoS scenario is relatively concentrated, due to the limited number of scatterers. However, the sub-THz channel does not show increased sparsity, as strong first-order

reflections, such as those from the doors behind the Tx, remain significant. This is reflected in the temporal domain, where the delay spread increases from 0.87 ns at mm-wave to 2.03 ns at sub-THz, likely due to additional weak reflections.

(a) PADP at 25-27.5 GHz Scenario 3.A

(b) PADP at 99-101.5 GHz Scenario 3.A

Fig. 9: Representation of the PADPs for the in-vehicle LoS link (Scenario 3.A) at mm-wave and sub-THz frequencies, highlighting the main MPCs. Temporal resolution: 0.40 ns.

O2V-OLoS links (Scenarios 4.A-B): Fig. 11 (a) and (b) report the PADPs for Scenario 4.A and 4.B, respectively.

Cluster 1 corresponds to the direct radial path between the two face-to-face antennas. The second and third clusters originate from symmetric directions, with AOAs of approximately $\pm 60^\circ$, and are likely caused by diffractions at the vertical edges of the trunk door, very close to the Reflection Shadow Boundary (RSB) and represented by the yellow trajectory in Fig. 12. Cluster 4 consists of backscattering components originating from the car interior, primarily from the rear seat backrest (green trajectory in Fig.12). These appear around an AOA of $\pm 180^\circ$, which is consistent with the front-to-back antenna configuration, and are split into two due to the 360°

Fig. 10: Interpretation of the PADP for the in-vehicle LoS scenario with Rx and Tx on the rear seats of the car, highlighting the geometric paths of the main MPCs

(a) PADP Scenario 4.A

(b) PADP Scenario 4.B

Fig. 11: Representation of the PADPs for the O2V-OLoS links (Scenarios 4.A and 4.B) at 8-12 GHz, highlighting the main MPCs. Temporal resolution: 0.25 ns.

angular periodicity of the plot.

In addition to these clusters, Fig. 11 (a) reveals a background of weaker, densely distributed multipath components with higher delays, likely resulting from multiple internal reflections and diffuse scattering.

Scenario 4.B shows three dominant MPCs, whose geometric interpretation is illustrated in Fig. 13. The strongest path corresponds to a radial trajectory passing through the rear window, with an AOA of approximately $110\text{--}120^\circ$ and a path length of 4.5 m, aligned with the direction of the face-to-face antennas. The second path, with an AOA of around 140° and a length of 4.9 m, likely results from diffraction at the horizontal edge of the door, near the ISB. The third path appears at an AOA of approximately 110° and a delay of 22 ns, and is attributed to a single-bounce reflection from the door on the opposite side of the transmitter.

As expected, the angular spread in Scenarios 4.A and 4.B is larger than in Scenario 3.A, due to the OLoS conditions. In the absence of a dominant line-of-sight path, the MPCs arrive from a broader range of directions, driven by stronger contributions from reflected and scattered components. This is also reflected in the temporal domain: τ_{RMS} is 4.49 ns in Scenario 4.A and 4.8 ns in Scenario 4.B, both higher than in Scenario 3.A. The increased delay spread further confirms the presence of multiple propagation paths with longer excess delays, consistent with a richer multipath environment in O2V scenarios under OLoS conditions.

In O2V scenarios it is also observed a major role of diffracted paths on the metal car body, typically on the door and window edges and in configurations where the AOAs are close to the ISB or RSB shadow boundaries.

Fig. 12: Interpretation of the PADP for scenario 4.A at 8-12 GHz, highlighting the geometric paths of the main MPCs. Tx is near the trunk and Rx is mounted on the rotator inside the car.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents multi-band, multidimensional, in-vehicle and outdoor-to-vehicle radio channel measurements for 6G sub-networks. A comprehensive analysis has been

Fig. 13: Interpretation of the PADP for scenario 4.B at 8-12 GHz, highlighting the geometric paths of the main MPCs. Tx is near the rear door and Rx is mounted on the rotator inside the car.

conducted in terms of path-loss, fading characteristics and angular/delay dispersion based on measurements on a few different, real-world car models. The work is motivated by the fact that car manufacturers, although aware of the importance of radio propagation for dedicated connectivity and radar applications, are still far from designing vehicles with future-generation wireless systems in mind. Therefore a thorough characterization of in-vehicle and outdoor-to-vehicle propagation is surely needed. For what concerns path loss, the study shows that multipath reverberation within the vehicle allows for a slight gain with respect to free space in LoS cases at lower frequencies, whereas OLoS cases appear to be often unfeasible at mm-wave and sub-THz frequencies due to the significant excess loss due to cluttering. Nevertheless, reflection from the car ceiling could be used in such cases to ensure connectivity. Regarding multipath dispersion, results show a very low RMS delay spread of around 1 ns and a moderate angle spread of about 30° for in-vehicle, omnidirectional links, with dispersion figures further decreasing with frequency. Interestingly, O2V links with directive Tx antenna show a much higher degree of dispersion, with angle spreads of up to 90° and delay spreads of about 5 ns.

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